

FEATURES OF APPLYING AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14209318>

Turgunova Farida Maxammadjanovna^{1,2}

¹Doctoral student at Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, Andijan, Uzbekistan

²University of Journalism and Mass Communication of Uzbekistan, Tashkent,

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the features of the integrative approach in the development of foreign language communicative competence in the modern educational process. It is proposed to introduce specially developed industry-specific English language teaching programs into the educational process at non-philological universities. It is shown that at the current level of development of methods of teaching a foreign language, the priority of the teacher’s activity is the formation in students of the required level of communicative competence, which is associated with combining knowledge in different disciplines. It is also confirmed that learning based on an integrative approach allows students to establish connections between different subjects and contributes to a deeper assimilation of educational material.

Keywords: *speech skills, integrative approach, communicative competence*

In the conditions of modern globalization and integration, effective educational technologies are being created in the higher education system of many countries around the world, making it possible to train highly qualified and in-demand personnel using integrative approaches. In this regard, in our country, in order to popularize the experience of leading foreign countries in all areas of higher education, in particular in the field of pedagogy, the experience of countries such as Great Britain, Finland, Japan, and South Korea is used. Work is underway to introduce and disseminate modern pedagogical models of an integrated approach into the educational system.

In recent years, a number of universities in our country have begun to regularly introduce specially developed industry-specific English language teaching programs. In the context of international globalization, it is desirable for future specialists to have not only a load of subjects and the quality of the educational standard, but also the ability to clearly and fluently express their thoughts in foreign languages and master special vocabulary. Therefore, fluency in English is emphasized and

encouraged in the English language curriculum from primary school to higher education in modern Uzbekistan. However, at present, the government of our country pays special attention to this area, and such skills are officially assessed both at school and at university entrance exams, which allows the possession of certain benefits.

As practice shows, many students, when faced with the tasks of spoken English, face a number of obstacles when expressing opinions, holding discussions or communicating with their teachers or classmates in English classes.

In the modern educational process, an integrative approach to the development of foreign language communicative competence is one of the effective ways to increase students' motivation to successfully study at a university [A.Belyaev & M.Evstigneev, 2024; I.Zimnyaya & E.Zemtsova, 2008; U.Umirziyev, 2021; S.Uljayeva, 2023]. Therefore, an integrative approach is used in the preparation of work programs and teaching aids in subjects that involve the development of foreign language communicative competence. The integrative approach plays a major role in modernizing and improving the educational process in universities. Currently, this approach is being actively introduced into the educational process and helps students adapt to different subjects.

At the current level of development of methods of teaching a foreign language, the priority of a teacher at a non-philological university is the formation in students of the necessary level of communicative competence, sufficient to ensure their academic mobility. That is, within the framework of a multi-level, multifaceted education system, the student's opportunities and his potential lie in choosing different configurations of his education depending on changing environmental conditions and employer requirements.

Proficiency in a foreign language has become one of the basic skills of modern society, which, of course, requires the development of new effective approaches and methods, forms and directions for organizing the educational process [E.Atamirzayeva, 2023; O.Byrdina et al., 2020; W.Renandya and H.Widodo, 2016]. Considering the close interaction of all types of speech activity, the integrative approach can be considered an integrated approach aimed at teaching both receptive skills (listening and reading comprehension) and productive skills (speaking and writing).

At the present stage of education, interdisciplinary connections are becoming increasingly relevant, that is, education is moving along the path of combining knowledge in different disciplines. Foreign language lessons provide the teacher with great opportunities to form interdisciplinary connections. Education based on an integrative approach allows students to establish connections between various

subjects, helps them to gain a deeper understanding of educational material, and develops critical thinking skills. When parts of problem situations, each representing a different topic, are brought together, the picture becomes clearer and learning becomes more meaningful.

The ability to speak is one of the active and effective skills in the formation of communicative competence of students. This is a key skill in communicating with others. Improving speech quality, strengthening the components of speech competence, and increasing students' awareness of metacognition requires an integrated pedagogical approach that includes a training cycle for the development and assessment of student speech.

The following learning problems should be noted during the development of speaking skills:

- indecisiveness in expressing one's thoughts;
- lack of knowledge;
- influence of dialects of the native language;
- lack of practice and descriptive abilities;
- fear of making mistakes when translating your thoughts ;
- fear of making a mistake.

To prevent the above problems and strengthen students' knowledge, modern pedagogy proposes an integrated approach using an integrative approach in the development of foreign language communicative competence. This approach is carried out in the process of step-by-step use of the communicative-activity method of developing the student's communicative and language skills.

Thus, the integrative approach serves as a tool to overcome all of the above problems and provide sufficient practice and confidence in the development of the student's speech skills. Through an integrated approach, students can have the opportunity to expand their knowledge in their chosen field and evaluate their practical skills. Through this approach, students can have the opportunity to develop their language skills, which will help build their self-confidence.

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